

**THE ROLE OF NATIONAL INDEPENDENCE IDEA IN IMPROVING THE
INTERNATIONAL RATING OF UZBEKISTAN****Mahliyo Turgunova Nuriddin G'iri**Namangan International University "Primary Education And Uzbek Language" Department
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Abstract. *The article discusses issues after Uzbekistan gained independence, which caused an active search for the concept and principles of the national idea. The emergence of various trends with their opposite views on this issue. From the side, the country's leadership is once again finding the right way out of this situation. Development of the concept and principles of the idea of national independence, which have become a reliable ideological foundation for the peoples of independent Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *national idea, independence ideology, national identity, nation, globalization.*

Intrroduction.

The gaining of independence for Uzbekistan caused an active search for a national idea, which lasted about 18 years. For Uzbekistan, as the most densely populated state on the territory of Central Asia, with a high ancient culture, tens of cities and thousands of villages, the most ancient centers of civilization, the problem of globalization is of high urgency. The main condition for the country's entry into the world market was the renewal of various spheres of life, including social, political and economic [1]. R. Baldwin's research gives an idea of how globalization affects the dissemination of knowledge and telecommunications, as well as the economy and society as a whole [2]. Entry into the system of market transformations is largely associated with the phenomenon of globalization of society, which makes it possible to overcome one-sided globalism [3]. Using of new methods and mechanisms, it became possible to join the world foreign economic activity. The government of Uzbekistan is guided by multipolar economic ties not only with the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), but also with the Eurasian Economic Community and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) [4]. In this regard, bilateral cooperation with the Russian Federation has also intensified.

Integration into the process of globalization should be based on the national strategy of socio-economic management [5].

The term "national idea" has not a clear scientific content. We can agree that this is a once popular idea, an idea of the desired way of life in the country, which owns its population. Such a unifying idea, concept may be useful, but it should never be artificially invented at the top of the government or implemented forcibly [6].

(Rostrum of the President)

For example, the idea of building a road to your house is unlikely to interest the neighbors of the person who had this idea. But the idea of, say, building a road to school will inspire many, because it directly affects their interests. Both personal interests (it will be easier for their own children to go to school) and public interests (children will not miss classes in bad weather) will unite around this idea. As a result, children will know more and will subsequently bring more benefits to society.

Thus, for the idea to be supported by the majority of the country's population, it must affect the interests and solve the problems of many people. Thus, the proclamation of the country's independence was at first a great dream. If this idea was not supported by the majority of the country's population, it would have remained a dream.

It should be emphasized that the modern period of world social development is characterized by the increasing role of national independence in the context of globalization.

However, as practice has shown, outdated views on the development of society and the state as a whole began to interfere with the achievement of lofty goals - the upbringing of a comprehensively developed personality. In this regard, the need arose for the emergence of new ideas and new views on society - i.e. development of such a system of ideas that would become a reference point in the life of every person, the basis for the formation of a worldview based on the principles of democracy and universal human values [7].

The relevance of the research topic is due to:

- firstly, the specification of the concept, the essence of social tasks, the role and significance of the national independence of the Uzbek people;

- secondly, the needs for further development of the theory of national independence of the Uzbek people in the context of globalization;

- thirdly, deep and qualitative changes in society, of course, require corresponding changes in views, since without a break in political culture, public consciousness, without fundamental changes in psychology and thinking, we cannot overcome the stereotypes of past views and misconceptions. Therefore, the formation of modern political views in every person in the spirit of national independence and sovereignty, the construction of a humane, democratic, legal, secular

society is one of the main tasks in the transition to a qualitatively new state of a democratic society in Uzbekistan;

- fourthly, the urgency of this problem is also due to the ideological interests of a sovereign state. As you know, the ideological vacuum characteristic of public life in the late 80s and early 90s of the last century in Uzbekistan was used by certain forces to instill and cultivate political instability, the formation of apolitical views in people, weakening of the political consciousness of the people, the defeat of religious fundamentalism and other dangerous tendencies that impede the development of national independence and political sovereignty of the Uzbek people.

The above fully gives the problem under research relevance.

In recent years, a large number of monographs, brochures, articles, collective works have been published on the problems of the theory and practice of national independence, which analyzes the socio-political factors of the emergence of the problem of national independence and state sovereignty, the main directions of its research, the concept and essence of national independence of nations and peoples.

I.A. Vasilenko, A.K. Seifert, N.A. Sakharov, A.Kreikemeier, M.Peshkov and other scientists made a significant contribution to the development of the theory and practice of independence and sovereignty of various peoples and nations. These scientists, on the basis of historical experience, trace and deeply analyze the main factors of the emergence, the historical need for the acquisition of national independence and state sovereignty.

On the problems of trilingualism in the country (Uzbek, Russian and English), for a long time there has been an extensive discussion in newspapers and magazines, at seminars and conferences. Over time, they began to find greater understanding and concretize the main provisions of the national ideology, which helped the population of Uzbekistan to realize their rich spiritual world and restore national dignity, infringed upon during the years of the Soviet past. Of course, distortions also appeared when some socialists began to exalt the national idea immensely. This exaggeration was reflected, for example, in two questions:

the national idea was sometimes put above universal human values;

there were proposals to consolidate the status of the Uzbeks as the titular nation.

Both directions could lead to negative consequences for the spiritual atmosphere of multinational Uzbekistan.

With the participation of proposals from the scientific community, the country's leadership was able to find the right way out of this situation.

In the well-known book by Karimov Islam Abduganevich "The Idea of National Independence: Basic Concepts and Principles" all the accents were set correctly, instead of a purely national idea that could lead to a misinterpretation of the national question, the idea of national independence was proclaimed. Over the past few years, it has become clear that the adjusted policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in this matter was an example of a methodologically correct solution to the national question in a difficult transition period.

Some Uzbek sociologists believe (N. Ismatova, R. Tanisheva and R. Kurban-Magomedova) that ethnic identity largely depends on the characteristics of the political, economic, cultural life of society. Indeed, when Uzbekistan was part of the USSR, its ethnic identity was determined by the nationwide identity of a single country, which predetermined all models of behavior of individual republics. That is, at that time the problems of ethnic identity were predetermined by the very fact of Uzbekistan's stay in the USSR.

After 1991, national, but not political, identity became the main criterion for Uzbekistan, determining its further development. In an independent state, civilizational identity (cultural, national, religious) becomes predominant and largely influences politics and economics.

At the same time, one cannot agree that a society can lose its stable identity in such a short time. This can be confirmed by the fact that the indigenous peoples of Uzbekistan have not lost their fundamental identity in more than 70 years of the Soviet period. It is easier to lose identification at the national level than national identity. This is happening now, for example, in European countries.

Currently, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromovich Mirziyoyev pursues a balanced, active and pragmatic policy, calculated on his own strength, without undue reliance on major world powers. He proposed a new national idea - to make the inhabitants of the country, and accordingly the state, rich. In this connection, the President should be especially noted to concentrate on solving urgent internal problems. Prospects for strengthening relations with the Central Asian states. Uzbekistan abandoned the previous policy of limited regional cooperation, laid a solid foundation for solving decades of unsolved problems, united the region with friendly ties, thereby creating an atmosphere of stability. Undoubtedly, the quintessence of the entire ideology of national independence of the state of Uzbekistan is concentrated in this mission.

In accordance with the Action Strategy, taking into account the outlined priority tasks, the issue of developing the national idea is relevant. Since the adoption of the order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop a Concept for the development of a national idea at a new stage of development of Uzbekistan" dated April 8, 2019, a number of works have been completed. In particular, a working group consisting of renowned scientists, experts, and creative intelligentsia developed a draft Concept of the National Idea.

A single national idea of a multinational people at today's new stage of development of Uzbekistan embodies not only the positive world experience in the spiritual and educational, but also in the socio-political and economic spheres, has absorbed, in particular, such important achievements associated with increasing the intellectual potential personality and human capital development.

This concept reflects the most important tasks that must be carried out in our country on the basis of the idea of a national upsurge. The idea of national upsurge combines such principles as strengthening peace, civil and interethnic harmony, tolerance, full establishment of democratic principles, development of human rights and freedoms, the rule of law and justice, material and spiritual life in our country. At the conference, opinions and proposals were expressed for further improving the concept.

Conclusions. The idea of national independence and an orientation towards a sharp improvement in the life of the population has become a reliable ideological foundation for the peoples of independent Uzbekistan. In order to make the process of strengthening and developing independence and sovereignty effective, it is necessary to strengthen the practical activities of spiritual and ideological institutions in the fight against extremism, Islamic fundamentalism, nationalist views, to disclose their reactionary nature and harm, to give a timely and evidence-based rebuff, to expose any and all tricks of the hostile propaganda to weaken the national independence and sovereignty of the Uzbek statehood.

Nevertheless, the strengthening and further development of national independence and sovereignty, we consider it expedient to intensify the activities of all democratic forces of society, state bodies, political parties, public and religious organizations of Uzbekistan in stabilizing the

socio-political, economic and spiritual life of society. With the help of the above conclusions and recommendations, in our opinion, it is possible to effectively solve the problems of strengthening national independence.

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